

Risk Perception and Lassa Fever Prevention and Control Practices Among Healthcare Workers in a Tertiary Institution in Southeast, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Background. Lassa fever infections occurring in healthcare workers are predominantly hospital-acquired. This is due to poor infection prevention and control practices among health workers, low level of risk perception and late presentation to hospital for diagnosis and treatment by the patients, inadequate supply of personal protective equipment and lack of training of healthcare workers on infection prevention and control practices. **Objective:** To determine the risk perception of healthcare workers to Lassa fever and to assess the practice of Lassa fever prevention and control among healthcare workers in the institution. **Methodology.** Self-administered questionnaire to the doctors and nurses working at the entry points of the institution were used for data collection to assess the risk perception and infection prevention and control (IPC) practices. Data collected were analyzed using Epi- Info version 7.0. **Results:** The risk perception for Lassa fever among the doctors and nurses in the institution was found to be high with the mean rating (MNR) for all the parameters assessed found to be above 3.0 with the question: "if you develop fever after being exposed to a suspected Lassa fever patient what do you do"? having the highest mean rating of 4.92. **Conclusion:** The risk perception of the healthcare workers for Lassa fever was found to be good and should be sustained. However, the practice of Lassa fever prevention and control was not optimal.

Keywords. Control, Fever, Healthcare, Haemorrhagic, Infection.

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INTRODUCTION

Lassa fever is an acute viral disease that may be associated with bleeding caused by the Lassa virus, a member of the arena virus family of viruses.^{1,2,3} Lassa fever has been categorized as class A virus which may prompt a biosafety level 4 for management by the American center for disease prevention and control.^{3,4,5} The disease affects all age groups, but is especially severe in late pregnancy, with maternal death and/or fetal loss occurring in greater than 80% of cases during the third trimester.^{3,7}

A lot of attempts have been made at the prevention and control of Lassa fever after the record-breaking outbreak of 2012.⁸ Lately, the outbreak of hostilities in some of the regions in West Africa has aggravated the situation, thereby scaling up contacts with rodents that carry the Lassa fever virus. In addition, the escalation of poverty and the attendant economic and social deprivations has aided the spread of the viral infections to the suburbs of the metropolis.^{7,8}

Viral haemorrhagic fever has consistently been identified as a serious public health concern in Nigeria, Liberia, Sierra Leone and Guinea.^{9,10,11,12} The populations at risk in Sierra Leone, Guinea, and Nigeria may be as high as 59 million, with an annual incidence of illness of 3 million and with mortality as high as 67,000.¹³

Infection with Lassa fever virus has the potential for spreading from one individual to another, either within the members of the family or when family members are receiving treatment in the hospitals.^{14,15} Nosocomial transmission of Lassa fever in healthcare facilities represent a significant burden on the healthcare system.^{9,10} Infection prevention and control in healthcare settings has been documented to be an important factor in controlling potential outbreaks of Lassa fever.¹⁶

Lassa fever infections occurring in healthcare workers are predominantly hospital-acquired.

This is due to poor infection prevention and control practices among health workers, low level of risk perception and late presentation to hospital for diagnosis and treatment by the patients, inadequate supply of personal protective equipment (PPE) and lack of training of healthcare workers on infection prevention and control practices.^{17,18} Studies have shown that in the hospitals with improved infection prevention and control (IPC) practices, the transmission of Lassa fever infection has remained minimal.^{19,30,21,22}

The provision of required PPE and education of healthcare workers on the need for adequate adherence to the precautions on infection prevention is a prerequisite to curbing infection transmission and spread in the health facilities.^{14,23,24,25,26,27}

The devastation in the health system occasioned by the attack of Lassa fever in Nigeria especially in Ebonyi State appears to be worsening. According to the Nigeria centre for disease control,²⁸ 1781 suspected cases of Lassa fever were recorded between January to April, 2018 in Nigeria, with 408 being confirmed. The case fatality was put at 24.8% with 119 deaths across the country. This is the worst outbreak of Lassa fever in the past 50 years.^{28,29} There has not been a current documented assessment of the risk perception of healthcare workers for Lassa fever in this tertiary institution. This study, therefore aims to assess the risk perception for Lassa fever among healthcare workers in this institution with a view to promoting the prevention and control practices for Lassa fever in this endemic region.

METHODOLOGY

This was a cross-sectional study and the population was made up of all the doctors and nurses that work in the high-risk units (Entry points) of the Alex Ekwueme Federal University Teaching Hospital Abakaliki (AE-FUTHA), Ebonyi state, Nigeria. Alex Ekwueme Federal University Teaching Hospital is located at the FMC Road/Udensi Road Abakaliki, Ebonyi state. It is the only tertiary health

institution and the largest hospital in Ebonyi state. Currently, AE-FUTHA serves the College of Health Sciences, Alex Ekwueme Federal University, Ebonyi state as their teaching hospital where medical students are trained. The hospital has a 720-bed capacity wards.

The high-risk units of the hospital include: the Emergency Room Department, the Children Emergency Unit, the Obstetrics and Gynaecology (O&G) Unit, and the Family Medicine Unit.

Study Tool

The instruments for data collection used in the study was a pretested self-administered questionnaire which consisted of three parts:

Part 1: Social demographic profile of the respondents

Part 2: This contained questions on risk perception for Lassa fever among the respondents

Part 3: Questions on the practices of doctors and nurses towards prevention and control of Lassa fever.

Sample size

The Epi Info version 7.0 Statistical package for sample size calculation was used to calculate the sample size at 5% margin of Error and 95% confidence level.²⁹ The calculated sample size was 212. To make up for attrition and non-response, 10% of the calculated sample size (22) was added to bring the final sample size for the study to 234. These respondents were purposively selected from the study population. Two hundred and twenty-five filled questionnaires were eventually returned. Respondents on sick leave or maternity leave were excluded from the study.

Data Management and Analysis: The data collected from the study was analyzed using

Epi Info Version 7.0 statistical package. Descriptive statistics such as mean, frequencies, percentages and standard deviations were used to describe and summarize the data.

The scoring of the questionnaire was based on a 5-point Likert scale, with 5 as the highest score and 1 as the lowest score. Mean score of 3.0 and above was accepted as good while a mean score less than 3.0 was reported as low. Statistical significance of association between the variables was assessed using the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test with p -value < 0.05 taken as being significant.

Ethical approval: Informed consent was obtained from all the participants in the study prior to the data collection. Anonymity and confidentiality were ensured. Ethical approval was obtained from the Human Research and Ethics Committee, Alex Ekwueme Federal University Teaching Hospital Abakaliki, Ebonyi State, Nigeria (Reference number: AE-FUTHA/REC/VOL.02/2018/109) and the Ebonyi State University Research and Ethics Committee (Reference number: EBSU/DRIC/UREC/VOL. 05/054).

RESULTS

A total of 234 questionnaires were distributed and 225 were returned, but after data cleaning, six questionnaires were found to be improperly filled. Therefore, 219 questionnaires were entered and subsequently analyzed.

Table 1 shows the socio-demographic profile of the doctors and nurses in AE-FUTHA. Respondents aged between 31-40 years had the greatest proportion (49.8%). Those above 60 years were the least with 0.9%. There were more female respondents (52.8%) than males (48.0%).

Table 1. Socio-demographic profile of the doctors and nurses in the high-risk units of AE-FUTHA

Demographic Characteristics	Number of respondents (percentages)
Age of Respondents	47 (21.5%)
21-30 yrs	109 (50.0%)
31-40yrs	52 (24.0%)
41-50yrs	9 (4.1%)
51-60yrs	2 (0.9%)
Above 60yrs	
Gender of Respondents	105 (48.0%)
Male	114 (52.0%)
Female	
Marital Status	154 (71.3%)
Married	58 (26.9%)
Single	6 (1.4%)
Widowed	1 (0.5%)
Separated	
Profession	119 (55.0%)
Medical Doctors	97 (45.0%)
Nurses	
Current Department	61 (27.9%)
Accident and Emergency	70 (32.0%)
Children Emergency	32 (14.6%)
Family Medicine	56 (26.0%)
Obst and Gynae Emergency	
Years on the Job	33 (15.4%)
11-15 years	70 (32.6%)
6-10 years	81 (37.7%)
1-5 years	35 (14.4%)
Above 15 years	

Table 2 shows the risk perception for Lassa fever among the doctors and nurses in AE-FUTHA. The mean rating (MNR) for all the parameters assessed was above 3.0 with the question: "if you develop fever after being exposed to a suspected Lassa fever patient what do you do?" having the highest mean rating of 4.92%.

Table 2: Assessment of the risk perception for Lassa fever for the doctors and nurses in FETHA

Parameter Assessed	Number of respondents	Mean Rating	Std. Dev
Needles should be recapped after use on a patient	219	4.43	1.10
What is your rating of the mortality of Lassa fever if patient does not present to the hospital on time?	219	4.65	0.72
If you develop fever after being exposed to a suspected Lassa fever patient, what do you do?	219	4.92	0.41
How would you rate your risk of contracting Lassa fever infection from caring for a patient in your department?	219	3.81	0.99
Hand hygiene has no effect in the prevention of Lassa fever infection	219	4.63	0.76

Improper handling of sharps and wastes from Lassa fever patients can expose one to Lassa fever infection?	219	4.53	1.08
Based on the nature of your job, use of PPE reduces your chances of contacting Lassa fever	219	4.52	0.10
To what extend do you agree that Lassa fever can be transmitted from patient to patient and to a health worker?	218	4.22	0.10
How would you rate your knowledge and adherence to the FETHA Lassa fever management protocol?	218	3.36	1.03

Table 3 shows the IPC practices among the doctors and nurses and the facility's IPC practices. Some of the parameters assessed here showed mean scores of less than 3.0. These parameters include how functional is the isolation room in your facility (MNR=2.93), the rating of the Lassa fever management committee (MNR = 2.92) clearing and decontamination of patient's care equipment (MNR = 2.84) and rating of the level of preparation of the hospital for Lassa fever outbreaks (MNR = 2,81).

Table 3. Healthcare workers practices and the facility's infection prevention and control practices in FETHA.

Parameter Assessed	No of respondents	Mean Rating	Std Dev.
How often do you wash your hands after attending to a patient?	219	4.36	0.62
How often do you recap needles after use on a patient?	219	3.44	1.43
How would you rate your commitment to regular use of PPE when attending to a suspected Lassa fever patient ?	219	3.26	1.26
How functional is the holding area/isolation room in your facility?	217	2.93	1.06
How would you rate the availability and functionality of waste bins, sharp boxes washing points and PPE in your facility?	217	3.50	0.86
What is your rating of the Lassa fever management committee of your facility ?	218	2.92	0.94
How regularly do you dispose of used sharps into the punchier-resistant sharps container?	218	4.08	0.76
How often do you ensure that used patient's care equipment (shig, stethoscope etc) are properly? cleaned and de-contaminated with 0.5% chlorine solution ?	218	2.84	1.03
How would you rate the level of the hospital's preparedness and response to Lassa fever outbreak's?	212	2.81	1.00

Table 4 compared the level of risk perception for Lassa fever between the doctors and the nurses in the facility. The mean rating score for both the doctors and the nurses were all above 3.0 with the nurses' mean rating marginally above that of the doctors.

Table 4. Risk perception of doctors compared with that of the nurses in FETHA

Parameter Assessed	No of respondents	Mean Rating	Std Dev.	P-value
Needle should be recapped after use on a patient				
Medical Doctor	119	4.42	1.06	0.566
Nurse	97	4.51	1.06	

What is your rating of the mortality of Lassa fever if patient does not present to the hospital on time?				
Medical Doctor	119	4.60	0.74	0.244
Nurse	97	4.71	0.69	
If you develop fever after being exposed to a suspected Lassa fever patient, what do you do?				
Medical Doctor	119	4.97	0.28	0.111
Nurse	97	4.88	0.52	
How would you rate your risk of contacting Lassa fever infection from caring for a patient in your facility				
Medical Doctor				
Nurse	119	3.71	1.03	0.1006
	97	3.93	0.93	
Hand hygiene has no effect in the prevention of lassa fever infection				
Medical Doctor	119	4.63	0.66	0.9109
Nurse	97	4.61	0.87	
Improper handling of sharps and wastes from Lassa fever patients can expose one to Lassa fever infection				
Medical doctor				
Nurse	119	4.50	1.10	0.583
	97	4.58	1.06	
Base on the nature of your job, use of PPE reduces your chances of contacting Lassa fever.				
Medical doctors	119	4.48	1.10	0.522
Nurses	97	4.57	1.00	
To what extend do you agree that Lassa fever can be transmitted from patient to patient and to healthcare worker				
Medical doctors	119	4.29	0.95	0.3059
Nurses	97	4.15	1.04	
How would you rate your knowledge and adherence to the Lassa fever management protocol?				
Medical doctors				
Nurses	118	3.50	0.93	0.0516
	97	3.22	1.13	

Table 5 compared the IPC practices between the doctors and the nurses in the facility. Both professions rated the level of preparedness of the hospital low (MNR = 2.82 for doctors and 2.80 for the nurses). They also had a low rating for the functionality of the isolation (MNR = 2.98 doctors and MNR = 2.84 for the nurses).

Table 5. Infection prevention and control practices of the doctors compared with that of the nurses

Parameter Assessed	No. of respondents	Mean Rating	Std Dev.	P-value
How often do you wash your hands after attending to a patient?				
Medical doctors	119	4.34	0.62	0.436
Nurses	97	4.40	0.61	

How often do you recap needles after use on a patient?				
Medical doctors	119	3.04	1.42	0.000
Nurses	97	3.96	1.28	
How would you rate your commitment to the regular use of PPE when attending to a suspected Lassa fever patient?				
Medical doctors	119	3.16	1.13	0.235
Nurses	97	3.36	1.35	
How functional is the holding area/isolation room in your facility?				
Medical doctors	119	2.98	0.93	0.3388
Nurses	95	2.84	1.22	
How would you rate the availability and functionality of waste bins, sharp boxes, washing points and PPE in your facility?				
Medical doctors	118	3.52	0.87	0.886
Nurses	96	3.50	0.84	
What is your rating of the Lassa fever management committee of your facility?				
Medical doctors	119	2.92	0.96	0.919
Nurses	96	2.94	0.93	
How regularly/often do you dispose of used sharps properly into the puncture-resistant sharps containers?				
Medical doctors	119	4.14	0.78	0.217
Nurses	96	4.01	0.77	
How often do you ensure that used patients care equipment are properly cleared and decontaminated with 0.5% chlorine?				
Medical doctors	119	2.70	0.99	0.0314
Nurses	96	3.01	1.06	
How would you rate the level of the hospital's preparedness and response to Lassa fever outbreaks?				
Medical doctors	115	2.82	0.95	0.889
Nurses	94	2.80	1.07	

DISCUSSION

The study revealed a high level of risk perception among all the respondents in the study. The mean rating for all the variables assessed were all above 3.0. This is quite impressive. The key informant interview revealed that the risk perception of Lassa fever in the facility is so high that the trend now is the issue of over diagnosis. Every patient with fever

is now characterized as a suspected Lassa fever case in the facility. This finding is similar to the findings in the previous studies.^{18,30,31,32,33} The finding however contradicts the finding by Arinze-Onyia *et al.*³⁴ and Akagbo *et al.*³⁵ in which it was shown that over 50% of the respondents still recap needles after use on patients and only 80% of respondents had knowledge of Lassa fever prevention. This may

be due to lack of routine training of the respondents on Lassa fever risk perception and infection prevention and control practices.

The study showed that the practices of infection prevention and control by the healthcare workers and the facility is generally poor. Most of the variables assessed here showed a mean score of less than 3.0. Some of the variables include: the functionality of the isolation room in the facility, the rating of the Lassa fever management committee of the facility and the level of preparedness of the facility for Lassa fever outbreaks. Some previous studies made similar findings.^{19,36,37}

The study showed that there is no significant difference in risk perception for Lassa fever for the two professions used in the study (doctors and nurses). However, the risk perception for the nurses in general terms is marginally higher than that of the doctors. This may be due to the fact that there were more female nurses than female doctors in this study and females are generally more careful than males. This finding is in agreement with findings in previous studies on Lassa fever risk perception and infection prevention and control.^{26,38} The study done by Omotowo however revealed that risk perception level for Lassa fever was not related to profession.³⁹

The practices of infection prevention and control are essentially the same for both the doctors and the nurses. This is similar to the finding in the study done by Omotowo *et al.*,³⁹ Tobin *et al.*²⁶ and Wada *et al.*¹⁰. The two variables for how often do you recap needles after use on a patient and how often do you wash your hands after attending to a patient was found to be statistically significant in this study. This shows that the relationship between the two variables did not occur by chance in this study.

CONCLUSION

The risk perception of the healthcare workers for Lassa fever was found to be good and should be sustained. The practices of the infection prevention and control by the doctors and nurses were also found to be encouraging

in this study. This development will go a long way in ensuring success in the fight against Lassa fever infection in this endemic region.

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